

Building an AI dataset to estimate vegetation carbon using a QGIS-based annotation tool

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Keywords: Carbon sequestration, Biomass, LULUCF, Carbon sinks, LiDAR, GEDI.

1. Introduction

Recently, interest in vegetation biomass has been increasing worldwide due to carbon dioxide regulations. Accordingly, various studies are being conducted to identify local carbon sinks for carbon reduction. In particular, many studies are being conducted to estimate the absorption of forests, which are known as representative sinks, by utilizing remote sensing data to estimate vegetation structural features (tree type, crown density, tree height, understory vegetation, etc.). In the field of remote sensing, spaceborne satellites that can measure biomass include optical-based LANDSAT and Sentinel series and SAR-based ALOS series satellites. Recently, biomass measurement methods using LiDAR data have been attracting attention. In particular, GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) data is recently being utilized as data that can measure tree height and biomass with high accuracy through a high-resolution relative height matrix (Qi & Dubayah, 2016). In previous studies, GEDI Lv2 source data was used to analyze the vertical structure of vegetation in tropical rainforests and savanna regions and to estimate biomass (Silva *et al.*, 2018). Accordingly, this study proposes a method to construct artificial intelligence learning data that can estimate vegetation carbon capture using aerial photographs and satellite images, and to perform deep learning model training such as Quantized U-net, DeepLap v3+, and HRNet using the constructed data, and to verify the predicted capture amount using Spaceborne LiDAR, i.e. GEDI data.

2. Methodology

2.1 Vegetation Carbon AI dataset

The goal is to develop an artificial intelligence model that can calculate the amount of carbon captured through vegetation by building an AI dataset of aerial images that can distinguish tree species and images showing tree heights to enable time series analysis and prediction of changes in carbon sinks.

2.2 Data process

A crowdsourcing-based AI learning label dataset was constructed based on high-resolution aerial photographs and EAS Sentinel-2 satellite images. Based on aerial photographs and satellite images with a resolution of 10 cm to 25 cm, the process of distinguishing boundaries and assigning unique code values to objects of four tree species (pine, larch, other conifers, and broad-leaved trees) was performed. To this end, a QGIS-based authoring tool developed in-house was used to construct the process so that a large-scale crowdsourcing workforce could construct it (see figure). The crowdsourcing platform was configured as an environment where each user can perform work remotely on an individual PC through a dedicated server and cross-verify the constructed data. Naming rules were

defined to classify and store files of aerial images and labeling data, and the information contained in the learning data was standardized in GeoJSON format.

Figure 2. Data manufacturing Process

2.3 AI Model

Based on the National Greenhouse Gas Inventory Report, carbon output was calculated and a calculation method based on the international standard method decided to be used when preparing a national greenhouse gas inventory in the Climate Change Convention was applied. It was calculated by multiplying the wood basic density (D), biomass expansion factor (BEF), root-to-aerial ratio (R), and carbon conversion factor (CF). Afterwards, the performance was evaluated by applying the dataset constructed for actual learning using a deep neural network such as U-net. We propose a method to build data for artificial intelligence learning, and a method to use the built data to train deep learning models such as Quantized U-net, DeepLap v3+, and HRNet, and to verify the predicted capture amount using Spaceborne LiDAR, i.e. GEDI data.

Figure 2. U-net Structure of encoder and decoder

3. Result

U-net is known to outperform CNN (convolution neural network) that ignores spatial correlation of data because it consists of a U-shaped encoder-decoder structure that gradually restores information lost due to spatial dimension reduction in the encoder part through skip-connection in the decoder part (Ronneberger *et al.*, 2015). As a result, Quantized U-net showed better performance than DeepLap v3+ and HRNet among models predicting the capture amount, and the miou value of Quantized U-net was 76.22 and Pixel Accuracy was 93.01,

showing higher performance than the other two neural network models.

Assortment	Type	Grain	Size	Count
Airborne	S	10cm	512px	80000
		25cm	512px	80000
	GT	10cm	512px	80000
		25cm	512px	80000
Satellites	S	10m	256px	2000
	GT	10m	256px	2000
NIR image	S	10cm	512px	80000
	GT	10cm	512px	80000
Carbon Storage	GT	10cm	512px	82000
		25cm	512px	82000
		10m	256px	2000

Table 1. Details of Build Data.
(S: Source, Image & Height, GT: Ground Truth, Labeling)

4. Conclusion

The AI dataset created in this study can be utilized to build a

national carbon biomass map, and it can be used to analyze forest carbon absorption source certification work or emission trading target areas. In addition, it is expected to be able to support the promotion of artificial intelligence-related projects.

References

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